

SPECIFICITY OF BALANCE IN DISPOSAL (WEIGHTLIFTING)**Nikolina Dimitrova***Department for Foreign Languages and Information Technologies
National, Sports Academy "V. Levski", Sofia, Bulgaria***Abstract**

Objective: The main goal of this study is to obtain quantitative criteria for assessing dynamic equilibrium stability in the throwing movement in weightlifting. **Methods:** The study involved eight elite athletes. A preliminary experiment was conducted to determine the required level of weight to be lifted as a percentage of peak performance. The analysis focused on the patterns limiting the successful management of balance stability on an individual level. **Results:** From the expert assessment of the recordings on the trajectories of the generalized and private centers of gravity, the following conclusions can be drawn: the trajectory of the competitor's CCG retains exceptional stability and is probably related to a developed habit of motor stereotype, i.e. to a large extent, the management of one's own motor apparatus does not take into account the real existing. **Conclusion:** Classical mechanical criteria have no weight on the stability assessment. The adequate response of the control by means of the action acceptor turns out to be of crucial importance. The analysis of the obtained experimental results proves the presence of individual features in the strategy of the control system for preserving the equilibrium stability.

Keywords: Balance, dynamic equilibrium, weightlifting

Introduction

The problem of balance stability is at the core of sports-technical mastery in a number of sports disciplines [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Obviously, the concept of "equilibrium stability" can be significantly generalized and reaches the meaning of a category in cases where biomechanical analysis interprets the interactions between the external and internal force fields in the motor apparatus. In all cases, however, as long as the balance in living nature is also ensured by the control system - the classical mechanical criteria do not have the necessary significance for the biomechanical analysis [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. A separate cluster in this classification turns out to be the motor actions requiring control of an external inertial force field. Here, the motor task with the most extreme biomechanical characteristics is the "throwing" movement in weight lifting.

The main goal of this study is to obtain quantitative criteria for assessing dynamic equilibrium stability in the throwing movement in weightlifting. Achieving this goal requires overcoming a number of difficulties, such as the strong non-linear dependence between the kinematic and dynamic structures, the acute deficit of reaction time, the presence of an unsupported phase, the essential role of the action acceptor, etc.

METHODS

The study involved eight elite athletes. A preliminary experiment was conducted to determine the required level of weight to be lifted as a percentage of peak performance. The goal was to ensure a certain

number (20-25%) of unsuccessful attempts for the purposes of the analysis. The results demonstrated a strong dependence on individual characteristics within 10% to 25% of the maximum barbell weight. Therefore, the analysis focused on the patterns limiting the successful management of balance stability on an individual level.

RESULTS

The equilibrium stability should be analyzed based on the system of the common centers of gravity of the competitor and the barbell. The initial moment, when the weight of the barbell is included in the system controlling the equilibrium, is essential for the future development of the biomechanical characteristics. This transition forms a qualitative leap for the external force field. Since the overall movement has an explosive nature, it would be a mistake to think that the assessment of the equilibrium stability should be sought only on the basis of statics, as a balance between the two common centers of gravity participating in the system.

Here, it is not possible to develop an "absolute model" based on the example of managing one's own inertial force field (flying stance), both due to the functional-anatomical features of the motor apparatus and due to the predominant role of d'Alembert forces in the interaction between the external and internal force fields.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 present the typical biomechanical characteristics of the common center of gravity (CCG) movements of the bar and body for one successful and one unsuccessful attempt.

Fig. 1 Biomechanical characteristics of the CCG during a successful attempt

Fig. 2 Biomechanical characteristics of the CCG during an unsuccessful attempt

From the two figures, it can be seen that the location of the projection of the summarized CCG in a number of moments is outside the support area, and the stability is guaranteed by the appropriate development of the inertial forces. At the same time, it can be argued that in the initial phases the equilibrium was disturbed even in the case of successful attempts, and its restoration is not explained by the modulus of the inertial forces, but by an increase in the arms of their torques.

From the expert assessment of the recordings on the trajectories of the generalized and private centers of gravity, the following conclusions can be drawn: the trajectory of the competitor's CCG retains exceptional stability and is probably related to a developed habit of motor stereotype, i.e. to a large extent, the management of one's own motor apparatus does not take into account the real existing changes in the external force field.

This result leads to an interesting fact in our opinion, namely that the athlete makes very little correction in the control of his own motor apparatus depending on the real changes in the external force fields. This is probably due to the explosive nature of the motor action, in which there is no continuous sensory control between the kinematic and dynamic structures.

In fact, the overturning moment is only evaluated by the control system at the end of the last phase, when the static equilibrium is formed. Continuous control is carried out only on the basis of the kinematic structure, with insignificant changes in the spatial characteristics leading to very large changes in the dynamic structure.

Therefore, the control function of this difficult-to-control external force field does not have a smooth character and often registers a qualitative jump by mov-

ing the support area under the projection of the summarized CCG. A second visible result is the presence of a dependence between the tangents to the trajectories in the first and last phases of the movement (α and β).

The statistical analysis of the established dependence between the angular parameters of α and β in the performance of all experienced individuals showed the correlation dependence $r=0.86$. Considering that different athletes have individual characteristics in the style of their sports technique, we sought a quantitative expression of these dependences in the repeated performances of the same experienced individual.

The calculated correlation coefficients in all cases had values above $r=0.92$. We obtained an interesting result after carrying out a deliberate selection, in which we excluded cases of unsuccessful attempts – the correlation coefficient is not less than $r=0.95$.

These results show that there are limit values of the starting angle α that determine the biomechanical expediency of the motor action. In other words, one aspect of this type of equilibrium stability can be assessed by the amplitude of the starting angle within which the athlete manages to maintain his balance. Another issue is that athletes with more critical values for α could have a more stabilized kinematic structure and, in turn, demonstrate equilibrium stability.

Therefore, the stability of the initial angle can be used as a second parameter of equilibrium stability.

This result is important for sports and pedagogical practice and points us to the idea of the possibility of improving educational and training work depending on the individual characteristics of the particular athlete.

Fig.3 Horizontal component of speed

Fig.4 Horizontal component of the acceleration

Figure 3 shows the horizontal components of the bar's speed, and Figure 4 shows the horizontal component of the acceleration. The mathematical description of the curves is the same for both successful and unsuccessful attempts, which corresponds to the stability of the constructed dynamic stereotype.

With repeated repetitions, however, it is found that there is a band zone of stability in the development of the corresponding parameter. Thus, the degree of stability can be assessed both with the criterion for residence time in the instability zone and with the point estimates of the extrema.

Conclusions

➤ Classical mechanical criteria have no weight on the stability assessment. The adequate response of the control by means of the action acceptor turns out to be of crucial importance.

➤ The analysis of the obtained experimental results proves the presence of individual features in the strategy of the control system for preserving the equilibrium stability. This fact could support the development of individualized methodologies in the educational and training process.

➤ There is a possibility of using functional biomechanical criteria to reveal the cause-effect relationships in the time series of kinematic characteristics.

➤ A reliable criterion for quantitative assessment of equilibrium stability based on the interaction between the external and internal force fields relative to the motor apparatus has been derived.

Note

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest was declared by the author and the institution.

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